

Cultures and Leadership for Integration (CLI)

All Cases and Contributions Convention Report

UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND
UWS

International Foundation
for Integrated Care
IFIC Scotland

Scottish Government
Riaghaltas na h-Alba

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Alyson Vale

Business and Operations Director - Abbotsford Care (Glenrothes) Ltd

Facilitating Change: Creative Approaches to Leadership Building a Culture of Innovation, Dispersed Leadership and the Rise of Next-Gen Leaders.

"We've created knowledge about culture and leadership integration through several key initiatives:

1. **Dispersed Leadership Model:** Implementing this model has shown how distributing decision-making empowers leaders at all levels. This approach fosters an inclusive and adaptive culture where staff feel ownership over quality improvement, creating a more engaged environment.
2. **Creative Leadership and Collaboration:** Encouraging creative problem-solving and collaboration has cultivated a culture of openness and innovation. This has demonstrated how creative leadership can drive both cultural development and quality improvement.
3. **Facilitation for Leadership Empowerment:** Using facilitation skills as a leadership tool has promoted open dialogue and reflective thinking. Leaders act as enablers, integrating leadership into the organization's culture and driving positive change.
4. **Sector Influence Through Collaboration:** Engaging in sector-wide platforms like Hivemind has allowed us to influence broader discussions on leadership integration. This has extended our knowledge and impact beyond our organisation, shaping industry-wide narratives.

Through these initiatives, we've deepened our understanding of how leadership practices can be integrated into culture, driving both innovation and quality improvement in care."

The integration of culture and leadership in our organisation has been made possible through a mix of key elements. Our move towards a dispersed leadership model has empowered people at all levels to share in decision-making, building a more collaborative and inclusive culture. Alongside this, we've focused on creative leadership and facilitation skills, embedding leadership into the daily workings of the organisation and encouraging openness and reflection. Nurturing the next generation of leaders has ensured we maintain our core values

while welcoming new ideas and innovation. Through platforms like Hivemind, we've also been able to broaden our influence and contribute to wider discussions on leadership integration across the sector. Ultimately, the supportive, forward-thinking environment within our organisation has allowed these practices to thrive, making leadership a key driver for cultural change and quality improvement.

"We've faced a few key challenges along the way. Shifting to a dispersed leadership model required a real mindset shift for some, especially those used to more traditional, hierarchical structures. It took time and effort to build trust and ensure everyone felt confident taking on leadership roles. Embedding creative leadership and facilitation into everyday practice was also challenging, as it meant rethinking how we approach problems and encourage innovation without overwhelming the team. Supporting the next generation of leaders, while rewarding, has come with its own challenges, particularly in balancing the need for continuity with the desire for fresh ideas and change.

Externally, working with agencies and partners has presented its own hurdles. They're not always ready to work at the same pace as us, which can slow down progress and create frustration when we're pushing forward with new initiatives. Staying ahead of sector trends and contributing to wider conversations about leadership and care can sometimes feel like a moving target, as the landscape continues to evolve. Finally, maintaining momentum and keeping everyone engaged in this ongoing process of cultural and leadership integration has required constant reflection and adaptability."

"We've learned a few valuable lessons that others might find useful. First, shifting to a dispersed leadership model takes time and patience. It's not just about changing structures; it's about changing mindsets. Building trust and ensuring everyone feels confident in their roles is crucial, and that doesn't happen overnight. Embedding creative leadership and encouraging innovation needs to be done carefully, with plenty of support and clear communication to avoid overwhelming people.

Supporting the next generation of leaders is essential, but it's equally important to find the right balance between honouring what's already working and being open to new ideas and approaches. Working with external agencies can be a challenge, especially if they're not moving at your pace, so it's important to manage expectations and build strong relationships where possible.

Finally, constant reflection and adaptability are key. Cultural and leadership integration isn't a one-off project – it's an ongoing process that requires flexibility, especially as the sector evolves. Staying open to change and making space for people to grow and lead in their own way will pay off in the long run." "There are still a few gaps in our knowledge about culture and leadership integration (CLI) that are worth exploring further. One area is how to better measure the impact in real-time. While we've seen positive changes, it would be useful to have clearer data on exactly how this model is affecting both culture and outcomes on a day-to-day basis. Really emphasising the importance of how qualitative data can be better harnessed.

We're also still learning about how best to support the next generation of leaders while maintaining continuity. Balancing innovation with tradition is tricky and finding the right framework to ensure new leaders are fully empowered without losing sight of core values is something we're still refining.

Another gap is understanding how to navigate external relationships more effectively, especially with agencies or partners that aren't working at the same speed. There's a lot to explore in terms of creating smoother collaborations and managing external expectations while keeping our own momentum going.

Lastly, while we've made progress in embedding creative leadership and facilitation skills, we're still exploring how to make this a more natural part of everyday practice across all levels of the organisation, without it feeling forced or like an extra layer of work. These are areas that would benefit from deeper exploration as we continue to evolve our approach to CLI." "Engaging in qualitative research, such as focus groups and interviews with staff at all levels, could help us understand the nuances of how leadership integration is experienced across the organisation. This would give us a more human perspective on the impact of our initiatives and highlight areas where more support or clarity is needed.

Lastly, collaborative research projects with external partners, particularly around managing relationships and expectations, could be beneficial. Sharing best practices, challenges, and successes with others in the sector might help us refine how we work with external agencies and partners, especially when their pace or priorities don't align with ours. Combining these methods would give us a more holistic understanding and help us refine our approach."

<https://relationshipsproject.org/>

Dr Louise Henderson

Managing Director – Bon Accord Care

Interpersonal connections and supportive relationships to support integrated Health & social Care leadership: the good the bad and the aesthetically challenged!

- "PhD study that explored the value of interpersonal relationships and how they can help to grow supportive relationships across health and social care systems, sectors organisations and teams.
- Now managing a social care organisation (ALEO of local authority) where the application of those findings is seeing positive impact.
- Also learning from challenges of the past, that did not always show the best side of interagency working, teams and organisations." "Partnership working, especially through the difficult times and challenging conversations!
- Trust.
- Honesty/openness/transparency.
- Shared vision.
- Commitment from all parties and their shared desire to do things differently (sometimes for financial gain).
- A shared desire to 'make a difference'." "Distrust & lack of understanding. To overcome this, we led by example, shared knowledge and understanding, position, challenges, barriers, enablers and took a leap of faith to show our hand in the interests of building trust.
- Different agendas - To overcome this, we acknowledged the competing priorities in partner organisations and our own and looked to meet as many as we could in a new joint-agenda.
- Pressure from acute services - To overcome this we revised admission criteria and worked with key stakeholders to refine processes for transfer to our facility direct from acute services.

- Changeable operational landscape – To overcome this, we looked to build appropriate communication networks. " Integration is hard, working in new ways and moving away from the contentious saying 'but that's just how we've always done it'; however, when it goes well, it is the most rewarding feeling and people who use our services appreciate and welcome it because it really does 'make a difference' in their lives.
- REAL Co-design and production (not just tick box – yes, it does still happen!).
- Community Led health: Public services as partners (not leaders). Reform of our HSC system and the way in which we meet population health and wellbeing needs across Scotland.
- Practical guidance on building a solid foundation of professional interpersonal connections and supportive relationships between individuals, organisations, sectors and systems.
- HOW to break down interagency barriers – practical guidance for individuals, service providers, commissioners, organisations, IJBs, HSCPs.
- Guidance on forming a shared vision and agenda that incorporates individual organisations agendas too.
- The practice-theory gap can be very pronounced in integrated care."
- Greater application of implementation science.
- Monitoring impact: quantitative, mixed methods & qualitative studies.
- Action research – practical guidance for individuals, service providers, commissioners, organisations, IJBs, HSCPs.

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Louise-Henderson-3>

<https://www.bonaccordcare.org/>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36845871/>

Kirsty Merriman

Head of Leadership and Talent Management. Directorate for Health Workforce, Scottish Government

Improving Wellbeing and Working Cultures (IWWC).

We are a division in Scottish Government with a remit for leadership, culture, equalities and wellbeing in health, and in interfaces with social work and social care. We have lots that we can share about specific projects and programmes, that fit under the IWWC vision and action plan.

High levels of stakeholder engagement; user research; data and evidence from a range of sources – all influence our vision and actions, and the continual roll out and delivery of work.

Working across policy areas is complex, and setting scope of work is difficult and ever changing due to wider strategic context.

Engagement is key to progress. Engaging early and taking stakeholders with you leads to better progress – even if it can feel that you are stuck in ‘scoping/discovery’ for longer, it means latter stages are smoother how to better connect up across policy areas.

<https://www.gov.scot/publications/improving-wellbeing-working-cultures-2/>

Margaret Moncrieff

Chairperson. South Lanarkshire Health & Social Care Forum

Ensuring the community has a voice in the planning and consultation of health and social care services.

Representative on the IJB and Chair of an Independent Advisory Panel to insure appropriate community consultation of changes to health & social care services. Composed a Mental Health Pathway Booklet.

Part of a Community Panel to set up a UK Capital Health Impact Assessment Tool.

Current working across Lanarkshire to set up a Home from Hospital Leaflet for patients, carers and staff. Working "in partnership" with staff across health and social care services to ensure an appropriate training programme is available to ALL staff to ensure a "community involvement" approach to all work.

"Joint working and respect for each other"" is crucial to this approach!

Senior management need to be genuine in their involvement with the community and not only listen to views but act on them. There is a need for being ""open and honest"" and there are some things that cannot be changed, and the community needs to know why this is the case. The community members involved in this process also need support and training in their involvement."

The financial challenges at present are at the forefront of ALL decisions and, as we had a presentation to our recent forum meeting, I introduced this as " A presentation that the Chief Officer did not want to make or that we did not want to hear" but was necessary at this difficult time! We went through the proposals one by one and reached a "joint decision" that no-one really wanted to make!

Joint working" is the only way forward, with respect for each other and be open and honest throughout the process! Ensure senior members of staff know the benefits of community involvement and extent this approach to their colleagues throughout the organisation through training and support.

Katharine Ross

Senior Health and Social Care Integration Lead. NHS Scotland

Addressing health inequalities by reforming screening engagement and collaboration across health and social care: reflection and progress.

Through a 2-year programme, funded by the CMO Realistic Medicine Team, we explored how we can practically improve unwanted variation and differences in the uptake of bowel and cervical cancer screening programmes through the optimisation of integrated resources. This brought colleagues together from across the whole health and social care integrated system to acquire a better understanding of integrated operational systems, priorities, leadership structures and culture. This resulted in us finding a space in which to design meaningful preventative interventions that can reduce health inequalities and improve access to services.

In terms of organisations which made this possible: North Lanarkshire HSCP and West Lothian HSCP, NSS, North Lanarkshire Council, West Lothian Council, third sector organisations, independent sector organisations, LIST team from PHS, Scottish Government, Bowel Screening Centre (NHS Tayside) GP practices, amongst others. The willingness to explore what is often perceived as an NHS/health service through an integrated and social care lens enabled this research, and subsequent activities, to be successfully achieved.

"Differences in culture and operating structures - overcame this by gaining insight, understanding and an appreciation of why these exist

Data and information sharing agreements across social care, NHS and primary/community care services - I wouldn't say we resolved all of the challenges here, but we made significant inroads and in one HSCP achieved a 'near-time' data sharing process and agreement

Differences in terms and conditions between NHS and social care, inequities and the tendency to design in a siloed/speciality manner. We overcame this by developing WSM across the screening programmes and undertaking working on the value of prevention versus treatment - emotional and financial.

"This project identified opportunities for HSCPs and NHS screening services to personalise interactions and optimise the potential of local resources, systems, touchpoints, and

organisations more effectively through accessible, community intelligence that is both useful and relevant.

This approach also has the potential to support the current thinking regarding how we modernise our approach to health care - designing and funding interventions which support prevention, early intervention, and a healthier Scotland."

I think it would be interesting to unpick the reasons behind culture differences which drive the practices and behaviours which present barriers to better integrated thinking, design and implementation. I think having a better understanding of IJB practices, leadership and culture is important - and how these impacts of resourcing decisions across HSCPs and HBs.

I'd like to give this some thought but initial thinking is shadowing and mentoring opportunities - cross sectoral. We know the challenges - I think we need to get leaders working across integrated services so that redesign and investment fills the knowledge gap relatively quickly.

Derek Barron

Director of Care. Erskine Veterans Charity

Ensuring the community has a voice in the planning and consultation of health and social care services.

40 years' experience as a nurse - 32 in the NHS, eight in social care.

Have led various structural reorganisations which involved addressing 'downtrodden' culture in one NHS Board and addressing a bullying/fear culture in another organisation.

Was involved in integrating health & social work teams (in 1998 - 2004).

Lead Nurse for first IJB in Scotland (North Ayrshire), supporting the integration of health and social work.

Working as a team, openness to challenge the status quo, willingness to engage with others to listen and to adapt.

Challenges around professional silos; the politics of integration between health & social work. Engagement with the public on delivering change.

Openness to change - challenging our own assumptions around what motivates others.

The knowledge is available, it's about willingness to use it #listen.

Listening to those with experience. Involving frontline workers.

Stewart Mercer

Professor of Primary Care and Multimorbidity, University of Edinburgh

Primary care transformation and integration of health and social care.

I have evaluated primary care transformation and the new GP contract, with a focus on older people and health inequalities, including the external role of clusters in integration of health and social care. I am also evaluating new models of care for people in later life with the Advanced Care Research Centre at the University of Edinburgh. I have also evaluated integration of services for homeless people in Edinburgh. CLI is crucial to all of these things.

I gained external funding for evaluation of the GP contract from the ESRC. The ACRC is a £20 million new centre funded by Legal and General.

My evaluation shows major challenges in implementation of the new contract, in cluster working and in the MDT. These challenges have not as yet been overcome. Integration of health and social care for older people on the ground is patchy and the role of new technologies is under-developed.

Collaborative leadership at all levels is crucial, as is political will and funding.

Making it work everywhere not just in certain places and pilot studies!

Rachel Cairns

Development Officer - Lived Experience and Engagement

The Health and Social Care Alliance Scotland (the ALLIANCE) Supporting the role of Lived Experience Representatives on IJBs.

facilitation of IJB Lived Experience Representative network. gather insights and ideas, highlight opportunities and challenges for network members to share with key stakeholders. In partnership with The Coalition of Carers in Scotland, we published 'More than Equal, Valuing and supporting the expert contribution of people with lived experience' report, focusing on varied experiences of Lived Experience Representative Network and Carers Network within IJBs and IJB Lived Experience Representatives and Carers Representatives. Ensuring that all Representative's views, positive and challenging, were included in the report. Shared a case study showing positive experience and also included what reps felt could be improved.

Through the networks we recognise that experiences differ but there are examples of good practice taking place. There has been a shift in lived experience engagement and involvement, the positive changes mean that the roles feel more purposeful and meaningful, and progress shows the experiences and expertise of the Reps bring of value to IJBs. The aim is to showcase that it is achievable and to allow others to learn from and replicate it.

would be useful to gain more knowledge about the perspective of other members of the IJB and how they see the Lived Experience roles within the decision-making structure.

Engagement with members of IJBs, in areas of good practice and that, from the perspective of lived experience reps, fall below best practice.

'More than Equal' report, information on the IJB Lived Experience Representative Network.

Sara Redmond

Chief Officer - The Health and Social Care Alliance Scotland

Shaping the Future: Person-Centred Cultures and Courageous Leadership for Integration.

"The ALLIANCE has created knowledge about CLI through a range of projects and initiatives:

- Person Centred Voices – promotes culture change and leadership approaches based on the principles of Intelligent Kindness and 'What Matters to You?' across public services that enable person-centred practices.
- Integration and Academy Programmes – gather and disseminate successful examples of integration, highlighting the importance of leading with compassion and advancing a culture of shared decision-making.
- Lead Courageously – showcases examples of brave and compassionate leadership approaches through the sharing of personal stories by HSC leaders, people with lived experience and leaders across the third sector.
- A holistic approach to HSC including public, independent and third sector agencies in the future of integration.
- Working directly with diverse stakeholders including people accessing services, professionals, policymakers and third sector organisations.
- The shift to online environments post-pandemic hindered in-person forms networking and partnership-building.
- High turnover in Health and Social Care Partnerships (HSCPs) threatens consistency and long-term planning.
- Resources and capacity constraints for HSCPs and in the Third Sector.
- Human approaches – Considers human needs and human resources to build positive workplace cultures.
- Information sharing - using a variety of media (podcasts, reports, opinion articles)

enhances knowledge dissemination and fosters wider engagement

- Cross-sector collaboration - fostering partnerships across public, private, and third sectors creates a more robust and responsive integrated care system.
- Leadership at every level- People who access and deliver services should be empowered as leaders at every level. People are leaders in their own health and care.
- Power of relationships- a collective approach to leadership requires relationships built on mutual respect and trust.
- The ALLIANCE promotes culture change based on the five principles (ambitions) of Be Human, Lead Courageously, Share Power, Reimagine Investment and Measure Outcomes.
- Collective approaches- there is a need to continue to gather examples of leadership cultures where power is shared across public, private, third sector and with those accessing services. E.g. how are people and the community involved in commissioning processes? "

Incorporating the voice of lived experience in research is key to fostering cultures and leadership styles truly responsive to the needs and preferences of people with lived experience.

<https://www.alliance-scotland.org.uk/health-and-social-care-integration/person-centred-voices/wmty/;>

<https://www.alliance-scotland.org.uk/health-and-social-care-integration/health-and-social-care-academy/our-work/lead-courageously/;>

<https://www.alliance-scotland.org.uk/health-and-social-care-integration/health-and-social-care-academy/five-ambitions-for-the-future-of-health-and-care/;>

<https://www.alliance-scotland.org.uk/health-and-social-care-integration/person-centred-voices/effecting-change/;>

<https://www.alliance-scotland.org.uk/blog/resources/publication-release-celebrating-the-impact-of-the-what-matters-to-you-movement-in-perth-and-kinross/;>

<https://www.alliance-scotland.org.uk/health-and-social-care-integration/person-centred-voices/resources/>

Ben Farrugia

Director, Social Work Scotland

1. Structured multi-disciplinary engagement, at all levels, around personal, professional and service objectives.
2. Post-scrutiny support, to address issues with culture and leadership in specific teams.
3. Advice, guidance and assistance with the establishment of integrated teams; (4) Research with service leaders on what constitutes effective integrated (multi-professional / service) working.
4. Research, engagement and consultation overload among workers and services leaders ("please just let us get on with our jobs") - have tried to overcome this by making any activity as value added to individual's day job as possible.
5. Discomfort from service leaders and funders with feedback / findings coming from projects - have tried to overcome this by ensuring lines of reporting / commentary are agreed at the start, and free from interference (or the perception of interference).
6. Balance of system and political priorities vs professional and service user priorities - tried to overcome this by acknowledging the legitimacy of system and political priorities (e.g. efficiency) and make them as transparent as possible but ensure that professional and service user priorities are paramount.
7. Integration of service structures (e.g. management and governance) is not the same as integration of services.
8. Integration of services, e.g. multi-disciplinary teams, works better when individual's roles and functions are clearly defined and allocated, not when boundaries are blurred and roles merged.
9. The leadership competencies required in the integrated space are not necessarily the same as those required in the NHS or social work or social care, or any narrow disciplinary space.

We do not give enough attention to middle management, where the overwhelming majority of the work (of integration) takes place. We are too focused on the top of organisations (“the leaders”). And we still fall into a “leaders make culture” narrative, rather than a sociological or anthropological approach of seeing culture as a network of behaviors and norms, over which leaders have influence but not control. It is a lot messier and more complicated (and human) than a policy narrative usually wants to accept.

It depends on what type of integration is really the priority. If we are interested in integration from the perspective of the service user, then qualitative study must predominate, drawing on narrative experiences and researchers’ observations. Such study can draw on quantitative measures over time, for example correlating the impact on population health and wellbeing. But measures such as waiting times, discharge times, etc., while relating to individual people, are all ultimately system priorities.

www.socialworkscotland.org

www.celcis.org

Dr Lynne Douglas

Harvard Leadership Graduate

How as senior leaders across sectors can we best lever change by creating the conditions that enable change to happen?

My doctoral thesis looked at the readiness for transformational change across health, councils and third sector organisations through the lens of Christie recommendations. As a senior leader in health for over a decade and laterally a Chief executive officer in a housing and care organisation the practical application of leading systems wide change has been at the core of my job for many years. I have led some real transformations both across boundaries and also within health sector but working across many disciplines. "I attended a programme for leadership development at Harvard 'business School under a Burdett (Florence Nightingale Foundation) Scholarship. This brought together aspiring leaders from over 40 countries and from multinational corporations and also third sector/not for profit organisations to study aspects of leadership and change. It was doing this that inspired me to do my doctoral thesis looking in detail to aspects of culture, leadership and change across sectors. I have used this knowledge more as my roles have become more senior and feel privileged to have had the opportunity to expand my knowledge skills and experience in this important area

At a sectoral level leading change across boundaries of an organisation very much requires a senior leadership team including CEOs who understand collaborative ways of leading and individual who are comfortable with emergence and working within boundaries but not stifling creativity amongst those responsible for delivering change. real challenge is the silo thinking of many senior leaders (and Boards /Nonexecutive leaders) who have a mindset that is perhaps fixed and have only known a leadership style which relates to what they can directly control. Good leadership and cultures in an evolving and complex system requires agility, trust and most importantly a willingness to not just think about one's own organisation but also how collectively you can influence a bigger wider change. Lack of these leadership skills can make working in this way in a true strategic partnership very difficult and often hinder the scale of what would otherwise be possible.

To lead transformational change across the system and create the positive conditions within your own organisation senior leaders must not assume that they know what the micro cultures are across these systems but instead engage and listen so that when a programme

of work commences it is clearer what the true challenges are. Having a holistic intention to work openly, collaboratively and in an agile way that offers freedom to how the work progresses is key to this. Micromanagement by senior leaders or Board will stifle this more organic change very quickly. Working in a coproduced way with the people your systems change is trying to impact on is also incredibly important to ensure there is buy in and also engagement that is meaningful and positive to those persons or populations outcome.

“What are the leadership enablers and barriers in leveraging a positive culture of leadership in organisations across sectors. Who are the real players enabling or holding back true change?”

How can streamlined more connected policy formation at a government level help leaders implement into practice these initiatives. A key output from my research was the disjointed and contradicting policies arena that made it very difficult in practice to implement. We see this in many sectors not just Health but also Housing. perhaps we should find out how we could do this differently to align and reduce the complexity at policy level.”

Currently we are awash with policies, evidence and best practice across multiple domains - understanding how we go about implementing positive cultures that promote integration and good leadership practices is not a focus - test it is probably one of the most important questions to reduce the implementation gap that we see between directives and delivery (e.g. public bodies act, National Care service). Qualitative research to explore relationships and outcomes of change at strategic, operational and end user perspective.

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Lynne-Douglas>

Grant Laidlaw

Strategic Policy Manager – Scottish Government

Leadership & Culture: Supporting the Implementation of GIRFE, the adult practice model.

People with lived experience for the past 18 months through pathfinders and partners across Scotland – 6 pathfinders and 3 partners aligned to Health and Social Care Partnership areas.

Throughout this work we have heard people's person-centred journeys in accessing health and care. Insights from this work led to the co-design of a number of ideas and the development of the prototypes supporting the "team around the person".

Work was also carried out to explore the barriers and enablers for GIRFE to succeed. One of the themes from this work was culture and leadership.

The GIRFE Steering Group chose to prioritise understanding the culture and leadership requirements to enable GIRFE to succeed at the GIRFE Steering Group in June 2024.

We have held a workshop with GIRFE pathfinders and partners where we explored the Liberated Method and Intelligent Kindness.

GIRFE Pathfinders & Partners, Stakeholders and engagement with wider Scottish Government Policy colleagues in an open and collaborative relationship.

Widening our audience to system leaders across health and social care and beyond is our next steps to support ownership and collaborative design."

- Culture & Leadership barriers.
- Different cultures and agendas.
- Language and how we use language.
- Staff mindset shift - from fixers to facilitators (this is a big shift, and due time needs to be given to this to understand how do we make this shift.
- Making assumption that current practice is doing this already.

- Leadership not prioritising GIRFE.
- Perceptions of barriers can be a barrier in themselves.
- Culture & Leadership enablers.
- Leadership 'buy in' and creating the conditions for change - we need to change.
- Presenting the lived experience - very powerful.
- Staff need the permission to stop focussing on task completion and providing services based on targets.
- Building relationships across localities - professional courtesy, professional respect how does GIRFE enable this example of this could be an enabler.
- Give permission - how do we learn as teams / organisations. there is often a belief that there will be blame for errors - how do we move to a more learning culture and step away from 'covering our backs'.
- Presented as an opportunity for everyone to buy in and improve together.
- What are we going to stop doing to release capacity?

Exploring different approaches beyond those already focussed on.

Co-design, collaborative sensemaking.

Katie Morris

GIRFE Policy Lead – Scottish Government

Leadership & Culture: Supporting the Implementation of GIRFE.

We have been co-designing Getting it Right for Everyone (GIRFE) (the adult practice model) with people with lived experience for the past 18 months through pathfinders and partners across Scotland – 6 pathfinders and 3 partners aligned to Health and Social Care Partnership areas.

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- Making assumption that current practice is doing this already.

- Leadership not prioritising GIRFE.
- Perceptions of barriers can be a barrier in themselves.
- Culture & Leadership enablers.
- Leadership 'buy in' and creating the conditions for change - we need to change .
- Presenting the lived experience - very powerful.
- Staff need the permission to stop focussing on task completion and providing services based on targets.
- Building relationships across localities - professional courtesy, professional respect how does GIRFE enable this example of this could be an enabler.
- Give permission - how do we learn as teams / organisations. there is often a belief that there will be blame for errors - how do we move to a more learning culture and step away from 'covering our backs'.
- Presented as an opportunity for everyone to buy in and improve together.
- What are we going to stop doing to release capacity?

Mohammed Ishaq

Professor of Human Resource Management. University of the West of Scotland

Embedding the principles of equality, diversity and inclusion into health and social care.

- Caters for the needs of diverse ethno-religious groups - to achieve these services need to be culturally competent.
- Understands the needs of racially diverse communities. To achieve this requires outreach work in communities with the support of local agencies and third sector organisations as well as community gatekeepers.
- Ensures that human resources/workforce is representative of communities it serves.
- Provides effective training and development opportunities to develop and prepare workforce to meet the challenges of delivering services to a multicultural society.

Recently completed a study into the lived experience of carers from South Asian backgrounds who look after someone living with dementia. Participation from those with lived experience of caring made it possible to create the knowledge and understand the gaps. Funding from the R S Macdonald Trust provided the resources to undertake the research.

Getting access to ethnically diverse communities is a challenge. This has been overcome through exploitation of networks and contacts within various ethnic minority communities. This has been further helped through membership of various external groups and committees related to EDI. It is noticeable that ethnic minority (EM) communities face significant challenges in relation to care needs and only by attempting to engage with such communities through pro-active outreach work can we meet their health and social care needs. We know from recent research that EM communities don't feel that service provision is culturally appropriate both in relation to health and social care as well as in relation to mental health.

We don't as of yet have comprehensive knowledge about the views and needs of ethnic and religious groups in relation to health and social care issues in order to allow us to create an inclusive culture in relation to health and social care. We are particularly lacking in our understanding of the mental health needs of racially diverse groups.

Qualitative studies involving focus groups and in-depth interviews with members of diverse communities and engagement with third sector/voluntary organisations is key to gaining the knowledge required. We cannot rely simply on numerical data from surveys/questionnaires. We need more rich data.

Michelle Sutherland

Senior Manager - North Ayrshire Health & Social Care

Integrated Health & Social Care - An opportunity or a systematic process doomed to failure?

I have been fortunate to implement, develop, lead and champion integrated organisations, service delivery teams and community solutions over the last 20 years.

"In terms of what made this possible, it was by starting small - working with staff from different organisations on a small project 25 years ago; A new employability programme with a GP, private provider, social worker and an occupational therapist - and liking the different views expressed and approaches described, due to different backgrounds, organisations and systems.

My learning highlights the power of people and relationships, to find the best solutions to support and care for the most vulnerable in our communities. The creation of a network of 'change makers' who believe in 'the power of one' and each other; can make a difference. These change makers can also create an environment of safety as they 'rock the boat' from the inside, taking staff with them on the journey.

Communities and the people within them - focus systems on what really matters, reducing the political and professional noise. Communities can also drive change, challenge professional approaches and cut through risk barriers. It is important not to lose sight of the real reason why we are working in our Health & Social Care system."

"There are a range of challenges and from my experience the first step is to create a positive mindset to frame those challenges. Start with finding out what really matters to your Health & Social care system - find the shared things in common to all people - the workforce, the community and the stakeholders.

You can make a difference as our system is big enough for everyone to find their space. Identifying the positive and the opportunities makes senior leadership roles within our system exciting.

Leaders and staff still consume much of their energy focussing on the systematic processes and barriers in play. This is negative and mentally exhausting. The NCS will not create a single term of employment for multi-agency staff, standardise pay structures, a single IT system, a single commissioning system, a single financial system or even include key whole system elements that make sense on the ground e.g. GP contracting – so ‘park it’. These systematic barriers remain impossible to move almost 10 years after integration legislation – ‘so let it go’ and focus your energy on making a difference where you can at local level. “ “Be authentic – be you – the system is big enough to cope with personalities and difference. Learn as much about health and social care as you can – all of it.

Using an appreciative inquiry approach and strengths analysis with leaders and teams assists in identifying the areas of shared values, common approaches and a common vision. The approach also encourages people to share strengths with each other. Building a network of people who complement each other, but that are different, creates robust teams, that thrive on discourse, ideas and doing. Due to the political nature of health and social care systems, one of the greatest risks is ‘group think’ to respond to political priorities. It is important to remain mindfully independent.

However, if you don’t want to on a day-to-day basis work with multiple workforces, different organisational processes/systems and have to look communities and politicians in the eye – it’s not for you and move on quickly.”

“There is academic evidence that ambitious leaders, who create a credibility with the executive leadership by mirroring their leadership behaviours, rise quickly. However, Health & Social Care leadership is also technically and politically challenging. A leader who lacks technical competency becomes clear very quickly – especially to the workforce and communities – who see this individual as lacking authenticity. How does one balance the knowledge and leadership role expected?

Some academic evidence exploring ‘sector superiority’ highlights that for organisations that attempt to merge – they are only successful, when one organisational culture and leadership group takes over the other. How do we celebrate our differences and value each other?”

Appreciative enquiry, strengths-based leadership, and sector superiority.

Áine Carroll

Professor of Integrated Care and Improvement/Consultant in Rehabilitation Medicine – UCD/NRH

The role of complex adaptive leadership (CAL) in creating the right culture for successful integrated care.

Reluctance to embrace complexity but with gentle persistence that is changing.

Creating a positive culture in integrated health and social care requires leadership that adapts to complexity, promotes collaboration, and builds trust across diverse teams and disciplines. Complex Adaptive Leadership (CAL) theory is particularly relevant here; it recognizes that leaders in healthcare and social care settings must navigate unpredictable, dynamic environments. This theory suggests that effective leadership doesn't rely solely on hierarchical power but rather on empowering teams, promoting self-organization, and adapting rapidly to evolving circumstances. In this sense, leaders act more as facilitators than directors, guiding the system to respond to emerging challenges.

Integrated care, which aims to provide seamless, coordinated services across health and social domains, benefits immensely from a positive culture grounded in CAL principles. Leaders using CAL encourage shared responsibility and continuous learning, fostering an environment where team members feel valued and motivated to work collaboratively. By reducing silos and promoting open communication, leaders can align disparate parts of the healthcare system, ensuring that patient-centred, holistic care becomes a reality.

In practical terms, CAL in integrated care requires leaders to model flexibility, resilience, and innovation. For example, when integrating social care with medical services, CAL leaders might encourage cross-disciplinary workshops and regular feedback sessions to facilitate knowledge sharing and teamwork. They actively seek input from frontline staff, adapting strategies based on real-time feedback. Through this inclusive, adaptive approach, leaders can cultivate a culture where every professional feels empowered to contribute, ultimately enhancing both patient outcomes and employee satisfaction in integrated health and social care systems."

The practical application and also education and training.

Carroll, Á., Collins, C., McKenzie, J., Stokes, D. and Darley, A., 2023. Application of complexity theory in health and social care research: a scoping review. *BMJ open*, 13(3), p.e069180.,

Carroll, Á., McKenzie, J. and Collins, C., 2024. Medical consultants' experience of collective leadership in complexity: a qualitative interview study. *Journal of Health Organization and Management*, 38(9), pp.297-312.

Clare Cable

Chief Executive – The Burdett Trust for Nursing

Knowing, Being and Becoming a Person-Centred Leader.

In my role at the Queen's Nursing Institute Scotland, we co-created a Transformative Professional Development Programme, informed by awareness-based systems change (Scharmer 2007) and person-centred culture (McCormack & McCance 2017). This has resulted in 173 nurses and midwives working across community and social care having the opportunity to become creative leaders of integrated health and social care with extraordinary impact. "The vision of a nursing charity, committed to making a difference.

The wisdom and experience of an expert steering group.

The skill of facilitators who understand how to provide safe and brave spaces for leaders to flourish.

The willingness of participants to trust the process and step out of their comfort zones.

The support of employers to enable staff to have time to engage with personal and practice development.

The generous support of grant making trusts. Funding has been the major challenge, which has been helped by many applications to grant making trusts some of which have been successful.

Giving people time and space to step back, reflect, connect with self and others is key to personal flourishing. It is in knowing, being and becoming (transformation of self) that leaders have the awareness, courage and wisdom to transform culture. This is not a luxury, it is essential.

Finding ways to enable people to pause and become present to themselves and others regularly during the working day.

<https://www.mdpi.com/2039-4403/14/4/230>

<https://www.qnis.org.uk/impact/>

Harriet Hunter

Programme Director, Europe. Centre for Public Impact Europe

Self, group and system – finding shared purpose and working with the complex reality to turn shared purpose into a practical action.

“We have worked as a learning partner alongside people leading system change in public services. As a learning partner, we endeavour to support people to work together to lead system change and to reform how public services can really work to meet people’s needs in a human, relational and holistic way.

What we do varies depending on our partner’s context, but essentially, we support people through a process that can include:

- Exploring and understanding the context from multiple perspectives, creating time and space for people to hear these different perspectives and to create a shared sense of purpose together.
- We encourage and challenge people to step out of their particular organisational or professional viewpoint to inquire into what the people they are trying to support really need to live well and flourish.
- Supporting leaders to develop their self-awareness, to understand what motivates them, to become more able to make deliberate choices about how to respond to others and what action to take, particularly in uncertainty and in times of stress and pressure.
- Leaders play a vital role in convening people across a system and understanding what happens in groups, and we support people to understand what’s going on ‘below the surface’ in groups so that they can better act as a convener and facilitator of productive cross system conversations.
- Supporting leaders to create conditions for learning and experimentation, rather than performance management and managing upwards. How do you lead in a way that encourages people to listen and respond to citizens’ needs, and to share what they learn in doing that?”

Our experience is that a number of different things need to align for this kind of change to be possible – and that these things are never all plannable or controllable. One of the key things is a connected enough group of people with enough power across the system who really genuinely want to change things and work together to do it.

"Many and varied! Differing viewpoints on what change is needed, with not enough time, space or commitment to explore these differences. Not enough people with enough power between them committed to the same thing. Fundamentally different values and beliefs about what is important, what good services look like, what leadership and management looks like. Lack of self-awareness and readiness to be reflective and open to changing self as part of changing the system. Patterns and ways of working that just seem impossible to shift.

What we do find is that often as a learning partner, looking from the outside in, we can feel despondent when things get stuck or don't seem to be changing. However, we find out months later that unexpected things have happened, shifts have occurred. This kind of change isn't linear, and something that doesn't seem to have made a difference now may well turn out to have influence in the future. This can be hard to hold on to when all seems stuck.

I think that working in complexity means holding on to your intentions to change things, seeing every conversation as a potential opportunity for change, whilst knowing that you are not able to control all that happens. It means staying alert to how things are shifting and changing and being ready to make a move to act on new opportunities as they come up.

The involvement and impact of political leaders, and the relationships between political leaders and those leading public services. What do we need from political leaders, both at a local and a national level, and what support do they need too? What kind of relationships will really enable system wide change?

I am interested in action learning and action research, where those doing the work are using action research as a way to change things in their context.

<https://www.humanlearning.systems>

www.centreforpublicimpact.org

